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**PROSPECTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI), IN THE LIGHT OF
THE ADVANCEMENT OF HUMAN RIGHTS, ADMINISTRATION OF
JUSTICE, AND THE CONUNDRUM OF THE HUMAN FACTOR**

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ABSTRACT

One of the most contemporary issues in the field of law, is the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in legal practice. Although the pros and cons of AI are addressed by various authors, an important issue of interest is the fact that a wide range of factors, which are beyond the sphere of influence of AI are very consequential to its application in legal practice. Thus, through the analysis of case law, this research focuses on the reality that AI can only be efficaciously applied in a functional legal system, considering that the speed and efficiency of AI will surely have an innocuous impact in systemically corrupt administration of justice systems when the human factor is the militating element. So, the success of AI in legal practice, depends on the protection of associated human rights, such as fair hearing, and the right to trial before a competent and impartial tribunal, reverence for the rule of law, and the jurisprudential quality of laws. The State also has a role to play, in actualizing development, and providing other facilitative infrastructure that are required for creating a fertile enabling environment for the utilization of technology in socio-economic, legal and administrative activities/practices.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence, rights, speed, efficiency, justice

INTRODUCTION

As far back as the 15th century, intelligence was understood as “superior understanding” (Spiegeleire, 2017, p.16). According to De Spiegeleire, intelligence is the ‘cornerstone of the human condition,’ and the cognitive quality that makes man the most civilized, and superior to

all living things (Spiegeleire, 2017, p.16). Thus, over the years, innovators like Charles Babbage who originated the concept of a digital programmable computer; and Alan Turing and John McCarthy who played a significant role in the invention of Artificial Intelligence, have utilized their skills, and ingenuity in various fields of specialization to achieve the aim of improving the human condition, and for achieving higher levels of efficiency, progress and development in society. So, from the earliest advancements in industrialization till the 21st century, power, wealth and progress, have always being a concomitant of new and improved technology, designed to solve problems, and to remedy the limitations of the human person, by catering to crucial efficiency considerations. Thus, Artificial Intelligence as the name implies is a non-natural or non-biological form of intelligence, designed to offer cognitive assistance to users. From the First, to the Fourth Industrial Revolution, technology has been utilized as a means of aiding and enhancing productivity. That has been the case, from early technological advancements in ‘electronics, information technology, and automation; to more recent advancements in computer science, three-dimensional printing, artificial intelligence, and the cyberspace’ (Min, 2018, p.90). The insatiable desire for progress and development, enforces the expansion of the frontiers of science and technology, with the aim of leading humanity closer to the vanishing point of industrial and technological perfection. Hence, Artificial Intelligence has been placed at the pinnacle of technological ambition, as the quintessential level of machine development – by virtue of an attempt to make machines as close as possible to the cognitive level of human beings, with the added value of speed, accuracy and efficiency. Quoting the words of Franke Ulrike, and Bolter J. David –

AI generally refers to efforts to build computers able to perform actions that would otherwise require human intelligence, such as reasoning and decision-making (Ulrike, 2019, p.1). Artificial intelligence has important links to modern philosophy and linguistics, but it is not philosophy in the sense of a careful analysis of the language we use to frame concepts. It is instead an intriguing combination of logic, technology, and philosophy, a combination that might be called “philosophical engineering” (David, 1984, p.12).

INTEGRATION OF TECHNOLOGY IN LEGAL AND ADMINISTRATIVE PRACTICES

Obviously, legal practice is not immune to the modern trend of technological integration, which has pervaded most contemporary socio-economic, and administrative endeavours. Thus, observers have identified ‘a universal shift towards adapting AI into areas of legal practice’ (Faseyi, 2021, p.161). Such technologically induced changes have long been predicted, since the First Industrial Revolution of the eighteenth century as part of the ‘revolutionary reconstitution of society’ alluded to by Karl Marx and Frederick Engels as a consequence of ‘growing markets and ever rising demands,’ and the concomitant changes in methods of production ‘to meet the demands of the Modern industry’ (Marx, 1848. p.15–16). Consequently, the time and efficiency demands of legal practice, has led a significant percentage of practitioners to utilize AI.

Considering the nature and functionality of AI, Gottfried notes that there is a certain level of perfection the law is required to attain, in order for its interpretation to ensure justice, with what he refers to as ‘mathematical precession’ (Faseyi, 2021, p.163). The mathematical precession alluded to by Gottfried, is most likely due to the fact that AI might not be as cognitively flexible

as humans, so jurisprudential certainty, as opposed to legislative ambiguity, will be necessary for aiding the efficacy of AI in legal practice.

Hence, advanced levels of constitutionalism, are required for effective integration of AI in legal practice. In the same vein, only advanced levels of national and socio-economic development, are compatible with the utilization of AI, and technology in general, in public and private sectors. Using Nigeria for instance, the technological backwardness of the country has expressed itself time and time again. For example, in the technical hurdles that hinder the electronic uploading and transmission of election results to INEC's Result Viewing Portal (IReV). That was the case in *Ifeanyi v. I.N.E.C* (2024, p.295 – 296).

Jauro J.S.C affirmed that the duty imposed on administrators of polling units, to electronically upload and transmit results 'to the collation system and the INEC Result Viewing Portal (IReV)', is a technocratic measure designed to guarantee the integrity of elections (*Ifeanyi v. I.N.E.C*. (2024). On that account 'failure to use technology as intended can undermine the confidence of the voting public' (*Ifeanyi v. I.N.E.C* (2024).

Nonetheless, considering various factors that might hinder the utilization of technology, it was held that in line with sections 60, 62(1) and 64(4) of the Electoral Act; and Clauses 38, 48(b), and Clause 93 of the INEC Regulations, electronic transmission of results is not mandatory. 'Thus, failure to transmit results electronically cannot, without more, amount to substantial non-compliance with the provisions of the Electoral Act' (*Ifeanyi v. I.N.E.C* (2024). Hence, the fact that the government cannot ensure the functionality of INEC's Result Viewing Portal (IReV) during elections, is a negative indicator of the country's level of development. The judgment of the court in *Ifeanyi v. I.N.E.C.*, is an attestation to the fact that there are huddles bedevilling the seemliness adoption of technology in legal, as well as administrative processes in Nigeria.

Legal practice in Nigeria is still largely paper based. The development and/or deployment of AI in Nigeria is at its nascent stage because of several challenges the country still struggles with like irregular power supply, lack of internet or technology culture, poor internet connectivity or speed, corruption among others (Faseyi, 2021, p.167).

Nonetheless, technology is progressively integrated into various aspects of legal practice in Nigeria. For example, 'at the forefront of the technological drive in Nigeria is Law Pavilion Business Solutions. With their packages like Law Pavilion Prime, Law Pavilion 360°, Law Pavilion Case Manager and Law Pavilion AI' (Faseyi, 2021, p.167).

ADVANTAGES OF AI IN LEGAL PRACTICE

- 1.) Artificial Intelligence augments the labour of lawyer, 'put simply, given a prediction, human decision makers can in some cases make more nuanced and improved choices' (Ajay, 2019, p.32).
- 2.) It is a fast, efficient, and productive mode of executing certain clerical, data collation, information finding, and decision-making tasks.
- 3.) AI executes prediction tasks in legal work, e.g. possible judicial outcomes, prospective consequences of mergers, contracts, bail outcomes, 'scanning tax law and decisions to provide firms with predictions of their tax liability', etc. (Ajay, 2019, p.34–35).

DISADVANTAGES OF AI IN LEGAL PRACTICE

- 1.) In contrast to the dynamic nature of the human mind, which is naturally developmental; the capacity of AI is limited to the nature of its programming, and the range of data systemically engineered into the software. Thus, most users might have come across instances where search engines make empty replies like “no results found” or “this search is not allowed.”
- 2.) Regardless of its artificiality, AI is a product of human ingenuity. Thus, the prognosis or predictions of analysts have identified the likelihood of software engineers acting unilaterally without recourse to necessary checks and balances, or alternative expert opinions that are necessary for guaranteeing the objectivity and philosophical or jurisprudential efficacy of AI search engines. Thus, AI is known to be susceptible to –
 - (a.) Algorithmic discrimination and biases;
 - (b.) Weak transparency and accountability in AI decision-making processes;
 - (c.) Overly narrow ways of conceptualizing ethical problems (Camino, 2019, p.13).
- 3.) The competency of Artificial Intelligence in tackling questions of customary law is very questionable, because of its amorphous and non-codified nature that requires more traditional methods of research.

THE CONUNDRUM OF THE HUMAN FACTOR: CHALLENGES PLAGUING THE ADMINISTRATION OF JUSTICE SYSTEM IN THE LIGHT OF THE JURISPRUDENCE OF THE HUMAN RIGHTS COMMITTEE

With regards to the usefulness or prospects of AI in legal practice, it is a precondition to understand the challenges plaguing administration of justice systems, in order to predict what systemic conditions are necessary for seamless and efficacious application of AI in the administration of justice process. Consequently, the challenges of the justice system can be identified through case law –

(a) *Dieter Wolf v. Panama* (1988)

The case of *Dieter Wolf v. Panama*, involved a German citizen, who was detained at the Isla de Coiba penitentiary in Panama. He was arrested on 14 January 1984 on charges of having issued a total of 12 uncovered cheques, for amounts ranging from US\$ 25 to \$3,000. Nevertheless, he was released in 1988, so he returned to Germany. In 1990, he proceeded with his claim against Panama, in the light of human right violations, allegedly committed by authorities of the Republic of Panama. Thus, the communication implied violations of articles 9, 10 and 14 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) (para 1).

He claimed that his arrest was contrary to article 281 of the Panamanian Criminal Code, which affords accused persons a “grace period” of 48 hours to settle their debts, so as to avoid arrest or detention (para 2.1). Regardless of the position of the law, Wolf was immediately imprisoned at Modelo. So, he made a complaint, compelling State authorities to adhere to the law. Nevertheless, they reacted by transferring him ‘300 kilometres away to the island of Coiba, which houses a penitentiary for inmates sentenced to hard labour’ (para 2.1).

His right to fair-trial was grossly violated, because he never appeared before a judge, and had no access to legal counsel (para 2.2). He was tried in absentia, while detained at Coiba prison. ‘In September 1985, the judge sentenced him to three years and seven months of imprisonment on

nine counts of cheque fraud, while acquitting him on two counts' (para 2.3). He appealed against his conviction. However, the appeal was dismissed on an unspecified date, and he had no access to the written judgment. 'He then wrote to the court and requested the assignment of a legal aid representative, so as to be able to appeal to the Court of Cassation, he did not receive any reply' (para 2.4). He was not updated on the progress of his case, until judgment was given in 1988, four and a half years after his arrest (para 2.5).

The author posted bail in 1986 for a bond worth \$4,200. Nevertheless, he was rearrested the same year, on two additional charges of issuing uncovered cheques. Bail was revoked, and the author returned to prison. After his case was assigned to the Criminal Court (Juzgado Octave) of Panama – no oral public hearing took place; he was denied access to counsel; and 'was informed of the judgment against him in 1988, when still detained at Coiba prison' (para 2.6 – 2.7).

Consequently, while seeking remedy, he informed the Embassy of the Federal Republic of Germany of his arrest. He also reported that during his detention at Modelo prison, he was not allowed to speak without supervision of officials in the Embassy. After a formal protest was lodged with the Foreign Ministry of Panama, he was allegedly 'ill-treated and confined to a special cell, together with a mentally disturbed prisoner, who allegedly had killed several other inmates' (para 2.8). While in prison, all his property was stolen, he was starved for a period of five days, and denied visitation rights. Thus, officials of the German Embassy were denied the right to visit him at Coiba prison (para 2.8).

Also 'the author claims that, in each of the criminal cases against him, he was denied a fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal', he was not given an opportunity to be heard, nor to defend himself, or afforded the opportunity to engage the services of legal counsel (para 3.1). Thus, emphasizing that the ICCPR was grossly violated by the State, alongside serious violations of Panamanian law. He further claimed that judicial proceedings were unreasonably prolonged, spanning for a period of over four and a half years after arrest (para 3.2). The Human Rights Committee (HRC) held that the State's failure to promptly make arrangements for his appearance before a judge or other judicial officer authorized by law, amounted to a violation of article 9(3) of the ICCPR (para 6.2). The denial of his right to legal representation, constituted a violation of article 14(3) (b), in regard to 'adequate time and facilities' for defence (para 6.3). In regard to claims of unreasonable delay in the prosecution of the case, the Committee was unable to conclusively determine the validity of the claim, considering that 'investigations into allegations of fraud may be complex and that the author has not shown that the facts did not necessitate prolonged proceedings' (para 6.4).

The HRC also found a violation of the right to fair trial, as guaranteed by article 14(1), 14(3)(d) in regard to his right to attend trial; his right to be heard, and to defend himself against allegations framed by the prosecution; and the prosecutions failure to 'serve a properly motivated indictment' (para 6.5 – 6.6). The HRC held that the authors right to human dignity was violated, by virtue of the physical ill-treatment to which the author was subjected, contrary to article 10 (1) of the ICCPR (para 6.7). On that account, it was held that 'Mr. Dieter Wolf is entitled to a remedy. The State party is under an obligation to ensure that similar violations do not occur in the future' (para 6.8).

(b.) *Sirozhiddin Allaberdiev v. Uzbekistan* (2015)

In the case of *Sirozhiddin Allaberdiev v. Uzbekistan*, an Uzbek national, claimed the State violated rights guaranteed under articles 7, 9 (1), and 14 (3) (b), (c), (e) and (g) of the ICCPR (para 1). The author averred that he and others were unlawfully detained and tortured by officials of the Customs Administration of the Tashkent Region and the National Security Service, in a temporary detention

facility of the Department of Interior, in the Tashkent Region. He claimed that there was no formal documentation of the detention. Nonetheless, he was tortured, with the aim of obtaining ‘a self-incriminating statement in relation to a drug incident instigated by a Tajik citizen’, concerning a plastic bag containing marijuana (para 2.1). The author was arrested on the 3rd of August 2012, at the National Security Service premises in Bekabad, in relation to the drug incident (para 2.2). In order to provide legal assistance –

On 3 August 2012, at around 11 p.m., the author’s private counsel presented his warrant of attorney to the investigator in order to meet the author, but was denied access to him on the grounds that the author was not being detained on the National Security Service premises. Nonetheless, while in custody his rights were grossly violated by public officers. He was handcuffed, beaten with a truncheon, kicked and subjected to electric shocks. He lost consciousness on several occasions. He was tortured and detained on the customs premises until 4 August 2012 (para 2.3).

When transferred to the National Security Service investigation ward, on 8 August 2012, he was tortured to the extent that his left ribs were broken (para 2.5). Subsequently, he was indicted on drug-related charges under articles 25 and 276 (1) of the Criminal Code, and officially arrested, on 8 August 2012 (para 2.6). However, he was not afforded an opportunity to communicate or to meet confidentially with his legal counsel. He was detained there until the case file was transferred to the court in April 2013. While in custody, he was subjected to various forms of physical and psychological torture, in the course of attempts to extract a confession (para 2.7–2.8). Considering the situation, a request was made to the senior investigator of National Security Service in the Tashkent Region, attesting to the unlawfulness of the detention, and seeking an order to release the author on bail. However, the application was rejected on 12 August 2012 (para 2.10).

On an unspecified date, the case file was transferred to Bekabad City Court. According to the court record, the first court hearing was scheduled for 25 March 2013 but was postponed to 28 March 2013 and then again to 19 April 2013, on the grounds that the accused and the counsel did not appear in court. The author claims that, in reality, the case file was transferred to the court on 11 or 12 April 2013, and the author and the counsel were only informed of the hearing on 19 April 2013 (para 2.19).

The authors counsel alleged that his submissions were disregarded by the court, inter-alia, including his arguments against the admissibility of certain documents; his application to summon witnesses, including officials of the temporary detention facility, police officers, customs officials and officials of the Department of Interior in Bekabad that were active during the authors detention, all overruled by the court – ‘on the grounds that the investigation had not identified those individuals as witnesses’, in addition to other submissions on the inaccuracy of the court records, which were all dismissed (para 2.20).

On 6 June 2013, Bekabad City Court found the author guilty and sentenced him to 17 years of imprisonment under articles 25, 28, 59, 246 (2) and 273 (5) of the Criminal Code (para 2.21). The author claimed that ‘the court proceedings were delayed deliberately and without justification’, considering that only six witnesses were questioned in court; and that the judgment was defective

since it was based on the confessional statement of a co-defendant who was tortured during the pretrial investigation, and coerced to make incriminating statements (para 2.21).

On 13 June 2013, the counsel appealed against the conviction, claiming, *inter alia*, that the author had been arbitrarily detained and tortured and that not all witnesses had been questioned, and challenging the assessment of the evidence by Bekabad City Court [...] Tashkent Regional Court dismissed the cassation appeal as unfounded, rejected the request for additional witnesses to be summoned and upheld the decision of Bekabad City Court (para 2.2).

Consequently, the author made a complaint of self-incrimination procured by torture, contrary to article 7 and 14(3) (g) of the ICCPR; unlawful, arbitrary, and undocumented detention, and the failure of the state to adhere to laid down criminal procedure rules, which proscribed pretrial detention for alleged offences, which are punishable by less than three years' imprisonment; denial of access to legal counsel and facilities for preparation of defence, contrary to article 14 (3) (b) of the ICCPR; 'He claims that the pretrial investigation and court proceedings were protracted, in violation of article 14 (3) (c) of the Covenant'; he also claimed that he was denied the right to summon vital witnesses, while the prosecution granted hearing for all witnesses in support of their case. On the account of the author's claims, the Human Rights Committee, found violations of articles 7, 9 (1), and 14 (3) (b), (e) and (g) of the Covenant (para 9).

THE CORRELATION BETWEEN THE AFOREMENTIONED CASES AND THE PROSPECTS OF AI

As presented in the aforementioned cases, the administration of justice system is dealing with a wide range of challenges including –

- (a.) Execution of arrests with no regard for procedural guarantees, aimed at protecting accused persons;
- (b.) Disregard of persons right to legal counsel, and the failure of the prosecution to furnish accused persons with the facilities required for pleading the case of the defence;
- (c.) Execution of trials and sentences in absentia, without securing the attendance of the accused, nor their legal representative;
- (d.) Systemic denial of citizens right to appeal;
- (e.) Denial of visitation rights, or unsupervised lawyer client meetings in detention facilities;
- (f.) Denial of the right to fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal;
- (g.) Unreasonably prolonged judicial proceedings;
- (h.) Complexity of investigations, which makes appellate bodies unable to competently determine if delays in the course of investigations and trial were justified;
- (i.) Failure to inform accused persons of the reason of arrest, or the crime justifying the detention;
- (j.) Torture induced self-incrimination and factitious or fictitious confessional statements;
- (k.) Incommunicado detentions, failure to document arrests or detentions, and failure to inform the guardians or legal representatives of detainees of their detention;
- (l.) Unjustified dismissal of the submissions of legal counsels in the course of trial;
- (m.) Denial of the right to summon vital witnesses;
- (n.) Disregard for material evidence, thus procuring miscarriage of justice.

In the light of these challenges, it is important to note that the proper functionality of the legal system is a precondition for the usefulness and efficacy of artificial intelligence as a tool for aiding efficiency. In the sense that AI cannot remedy inefficiencies which are intentional procured by systemic acts of corruption, orchestrated by public officers. It is commonsensical that technology is designed to serve man, and man is not designed to serve technology. Thus, AI cannot aid a system that is systemically corrupt, because the system will inexorably operate how it is designed to function. For instance, when the right to counsel is denied, an accused person is correlatively denied of the efficiency benefits of AI which will have been utilized by his legal counsel.

Also, if an AI assistant has aided the legal counsel in formulating arguments, it will make no difference if such arguments are unjustifiably rejected by the court; or if the judged rather based the judgment on a fictitious confessional statement that was illegally obtained through torture. The efficiency and speed afforded by AI in the process of legal drafting, will also make no difference if the case is intentionally delayed or neglected due to political or institutionalized corrupt practices. So, the functionality and ethicality of the administration of justice system is an inexorable precondition for the proper and effective utilization of AI in legal practice.

CONCLUSION

Artificial Intelligence is an efficiency-based technology, engineered for the purpose of enhancing work speed and productivity, through various forms of assistance, in-line with the capacity and programming of the software. On that account, the operational efficacy of AI is only as good as the quality of its programming, and the quality of data systemically collated into the AI search engine. Thus, regardless of its disadvantages, like other technological innovations AI is bound to improve with time. Nonetheless, the only way AI can improve is if its developers pay keen attention to its deficiencies, and then, invest the required effort and technology in finding and implementing necessary solutions.

It is also important to note that in the area of legal practice, various factors which are outside the sphere of influence of AI have a consequential impact on its efficacy, which is the human factor. Hence, the government has to play a facilitating role to provide the necessary infrastructure, and the proper institutional culture to accommodate the integration of AI in legal and administrative undertakings. Reverence for the rule of law, enforcement of human rights, and the eradication of systemic corruption/institutional decay, are inexorable preconditions for the efficacious application of AI in the course of legal practice.

Also, since AI is designed to assist, persons have to play an active-supervisory role, especially in aspects of the litigation process that are beyond the competence or sphere of influence of AI. As pointed out by Fischer, the human aspects of the law involving equity, fairness, and advocacy are exclusively the tasks of persons involved in the administration of justice system (Fischer, 2025). Thus, counsels also have a vetting role to play, in confirming the validity and efficacy of AI generated information.

REFERENCES

[http://www.jstor.org/stable/20024925.>](http://www.jstor.org/stable/20024925)

[https://www.legalfutures.co.uk/latest-news/lawyers-using-ai-law-firm-to-recover-their-debts>](https://www.legalfutures.co.uk/latest-news/lawyers-using-ai-law-firm-to-recover-their-debts)

Ajay A, Gans JS, and Goldfarb A (2019) Artificial Intelligence: The Ambiguous Labor Market Impact of Automating Prediction. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives* 33(2)

Camino, K (2019) Artificial Intelligence. New Tech, New Threats, and New Governance Challenges: An Opportunity to Craft Smarter Responses? *Carnegie Endowment for International Peace* <<http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep20978.5>>

David, BJ (1984) Artificial Intelligence. *Daedalus* 113(3)

Faseyi, IK (2021) Artificial Intelligence and the Nigerian Legal Profession. *Achievers University Law Journal (AULJ)* 1

Ficher, WF (2025) How AI is impacting the legal profession

Karl, M and Engels, F (1848) Manifesto of the Communist Party. *Marx/Engels Selected Works* 1

Min X, Jeanne M, and Hi, S (2018) The Fourth Industrial Revolution: Opportunities and Challenges. *International Journal of Financial Research* 9(2)

Spiegeleire D, Stephan, Maas M, and Sweijs T (2017) “What is Artificial Intelligence?” Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Defense: Strategic Implications for Small – and Medium Sized Force Providers. *Hague Centre for Strategic Studies*
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep12564.7>> accessed 23 August 2025

Ulrike, F (2019) Harnessing Artificial Intelligence. *European Council on Foreign Relations*
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep21491>>

CASES

Dieter Wolf v. Panama CCPR/C/44/D/289/1988

Ifeanyi v. I.N.E.C. (2024) 10 NWLR (Pt. 1946)

Mussa Ali Mussa Benali v Libya CCPR/C/106/D/1805/2008

Sirozhiddin Allaberdiev v. Uzbekistan CCPR/C/44/D/289/1988